

Effects of Google Classroom Instruction on Secondary School Students' Learning Outcomes in Basic Science in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study investigated effects of google classroom instruction on secondary school students' learning outcomes in basic science in Osun State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was also to investigate the influence of students' gender on their academic performance in Basic Science and influence that students' attitude has towards the use of Google Classroom to teach Basic Science. The study adopted pre-test and post-test control group quasi- experimental research design of the survey type. The population consisted of all 10,256 Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) two students in all the public secondary schools in Osun state as at the time of conducting this

study. The sample consisted of 120 junior secondary school two Basic Science students and they were chosen using a multi-stage sampling technique. Two instruments used for this study were Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) and Basic Science Students' Attitudinal Questionnaire (BSSAQ). BSPT consisted of two sections; section A and B. Section A was used to collect bio-data of the students while the section B contained twenty five multiple choice items drawn from the past questions of Junior Secondary School Certificate examination (JSSCE) which were related to the topics taught in the class during the treatment. The correct option picked by the students attract two marks while the wrong options attract zero. BSSAQ consisted of two sections; section A and B. Section A was used to collect bio-data of the students while the section B contained twenty five items to elicit information on the attitude of students to the learning of Basic Science. The items in this section of the questionnaire was based on a 4-point Likert type scale with four options; Strongly Agree – 4 points, Agree – 3 points, Disagree - 2 points and Strongly Disagree – 1 point. The face and content validities for BSPT and BSSAQ were ascertained with the help of two lecturers in Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State who were specialists in Science Education. The test-retest method was used to establish BSPT and BSSAQ by administering it to twenty JSS 2 Basic Science students from outside the sampled local government areas twice at the interval of two weeks in Osun state. Scores collected from the two tests were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the reliability coefficient of 0.89 and 0.78 were obtained which were used to adjudge the instruments to be reliable. The research question was answered by frequency count, mean and standard deviation, hypotheses one and two were analysed using t-test analysis and hypothesis three was analysed using two-way ANOVA. The three hypotheses were tested at the significance level of 0.05. The finding showed that the influence of students' attitude on their performance in Basic Science using Google classroom. The finding showed that there was no difference in the performance of students in the two groups. This means that both groups are homogeneous. The findings of this study also showed that there was no significant difference between male and female students' performance in Google classroom and control group. The finding also showed that there was significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group. It was therefore recommended that government should embark on more funds for the

adequate training and retraining of Basic Science teachers on the use of Google Classroom, and that Basic Science teachers should be encouraged to explore and include the use of Google Classroom in their teaching and learning process.

Keywords: *Basic Science, Attitude, Google classroom instruction, Teaching and Learning Process, Academic Performance, and Gender.*

Introduction

It is impossible to overstate the value of science and technology to the growth of any nation. This is due to the importance of scientific and technological information and abilities to the growth of any society. The rapidly evolving applications of science and technology as well as the global reliance on its methods and outcomes in all spheres of human endeavor have made them so valuable that any society or nation lacking them runs the risk of being cut off from the rest of the world. The understanding gained from science and technology has helped to explain natural phenomena (like rainbows and lunar eclipses, which were once attributed to witchcraft and evil spirits) and free the society from the bonds of superstition.

It is crucial to teach pupils about science and technology because it gives them the knowledge and skills they need to create a society that is progressive. Science has been essential to the development of technology and has contributed significantly to raising the standard of living of people through advancements in agriculture, communication, medicine, transportation, and other areas (Omotayo and Oniya, 2020).

Science education is the only way to achieve scientific literacy and it is essential for a country to remain technologically and scientifically viable. The importance of students learning scientific principles, facts, values, and norms through science classes cannot be underestimated as understanding physical and natural resources in their environment and developing skills for their best use are made possible by scientific knowledge. This is laying credence to the fact that understanding natural phenomena and using scientific reasoning is beneficial (Okewande, 2021).

Nigerians started undertaking projects that may turn it from an underdeveloped country into a technologically advanced and independent one since the time of the country's independence. The first national curriculum meeting was held in Lagos from September 8 to 12, 1969, with the goal of enhancing educational initiatives across the country. The Conference Proceedings evolved into the 1977 National Policy on Education, which was updated in 2012 respectively.

The National Policy on Education lists the following five primary national objectives as the type of country Nigeria aspires to be a society that is free and democratic, just and egalitarian; a nation that is united, strong and self-sufficient, an economy that is great and dynamic, and a land where all citizens have access to a variety of opportunities (FRN, 2004).

The quest to educate students technologically motivate the inclusion of science courses at all secondary school levels in Nigeria. At the upper basic school level or Junior Secondary School (JSS), science is studied as Integrated Science, which is currently known as Basic Science. In terms of science and technology for secondary education, the Federal Government of Nigeria wants to:

- diversify curriculum to cater for its difference in talents, opportunities and future roles that would be opened to students after their secondary school courses,
- provide trained personnel in applied science and technology,
- equip students to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology,
- raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the dignity of labor and

appreciate those value specified under our broad aims and live as good citizens.

- provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agriculture, industrial, commercial and economic development (FRN, 2009).

In Nigeria, Basic Science is the first type of science that students encounter at the secondary school level, and it helps them get ready for the study of core science courses in senior secondary school (Oludipe, 2014). The consequence is that in order to successfully study a single science subject at the senior secondary school level, students needed to have a strong foundation in Basic Science at the upper basic level of education. Based on this, Basic Science therefore serves as the foundation for all other scientific and technological disciplines, (Oludipe, 2014). The Nigerian government has a policy that stipulates that 60% of applicants to the nation's universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education should be accepted for science-related courses, with the remaining 40% of applicants being considered for degrees in the arts and social sciences (Adeniran, Ochu and Ato, 2018). But in the contrary the number of students enrolling in scientific-focused courses in Nigerian tertiary institutions is decreasing while those enrolling in art and social science courses keep rising each year. This cannot be unconnected with the number of science students produced from junior secondary school level. According to Oludipe (in Adeniran et al, 2018), Basic Science, the first branch of science that students encounter at the Upper Basic Education level, should be blamed for the decrease in enrollment of students in science-related courses.

Basic Science is a practical oriented subject and ought to be taught in a way that students will be actively involved in its process of learning anywhere with teacher – students, student-materials and teacher-material class interactions Oniya, (2018).

Despite the importance of Basic Science as the foundation for scientific and technological studies, low students' achievement in the field of Basic Science has been documented by Ochu &

Haruna (2015), Oniya, (2018) and Ani, Obodo, Ikwueze and Festus (2021). These researchers went on to say that the chaos in the field deprives many students of the chance to be accepted into top institutions of higher learning to pursue science-based courses. The researcher observed that despite of making Basic science a core and compulsory subject at Junior Secondary School level, it is still seen as a subject on abstract among the students and the performance of students has not been encouraging both in internal and external examination which the researcher observed that could have been due to the type of instructional strategy adopted by the teacher.

However, the researcher observed that some teachers seem not to be creative with the dynamic nature of the Basic Science curriculum as they continue to bore students with coping of notes during the teaching in the class. They continue to practice the conventional, teacher-oriented teaching method. According to Oguntade and Akinwamide (2023), the conventional method which is often referred to as the "chalk and talk" method involves direct instruction by the teacher whose primary role is to pass knowledge to students and conduct testing and assessment. Conventional teaching or traditional teaching refers to a teaching method involving instructors and students interacting in a face-to-face manner in the classroom. It appears some teachers prefer to use this method because they are already familiar with them and they find it difficult to test new ones. However, a good method of teaching must be learner-centred, attention must be on the students and their learning activities.

Moreover, it appears that some students seem to be bored with the traditional face- to-face classroom instruction. This traditional method of teaching appears to have become outdated as teachers seem to provide the same repetitive lecture without considering the individual differences of the students. Oniya (2023) submitted that conventional classroom is known to be teacher- centred, students are usually passive and usually very attentive while the teacher explains the concept thereby making learning to be on abstract.

Conventional teaching is assumed to limit the opportunity for students to be creative thinkers. It is generally believed that teachers in conventional classes are not sensitive to the issue of individual differences. Mostly when questions are posed it is usually the very brilliant students that are quick to respond while others look on. This method does not give enough room for collaborative work and brainstorming among peers.

It also appears to be less interactive; students seem to be passive learners; teachers see themselves as know-it-all and the students get distracted easily. It appears that traditional classroom instruction uses a one-size-fits-all approach which does not provide the students with a personalized learning experience, it appears the students follow the same pattern and learning style regardless of their interests which oftentimes makes the class boring and less interactive.

However, there are innovative instructional strategies that makes students to be actively involved and there are platforms where teaching and learning process could take place without physical presence of both the teacher and students, and both of them will be actively involved in the process especially when the teacher and students are at different locations like asynchronous learning which encompasses an educational model wherein the simultaneous online presence of both students and instructors is not required. In lieu of real-time interaction, educational content and resources are furnished to learners, affording them the flexibility to access and engage with the materials at their preferred pace and convenience. Asynchronous learning is especially well-suited for individuals with diverse schedules and commitments such as online learning.

Online learning is commonly managed through a system called Learning Management System (LMS). LMS is a web-based system that allows teachers and students to stay connected with each other. It could help the teachers in the organisation of online courses, engage in several curricula, and interact with students. One of the most popular Learning Management System

(LMS) is Google Classroom. Across the globe, Google Classroom is used by thousands of schools and universities that aim to leverage its features for the enhancement of their teaching and learning process.

Google Classroom is a free web service by Google specifically made for schools with the aim of simplifying, creating, distributing and grading assignments in a paperless way. Google Classroom could provide an easy-to manage teaching and learning platform with various facilities for teachers to provide teaching materials online. Teachers could create and upload slides using Google Slide which works just like Microsoft PowerPoint, teachers could upload or stream live videos from both YouTube and other video platforms, besides, teachers could as well upload questions using Google form which could be used in assessing students' learning outcomes. Moreover, teachers could easily share files with students using Google Drive without the fear of losing these files as they are automatically backed up to the cloud. Therefore, the teacher could recollect and reuse a file or document.

The main aim of Google Classroom is to restructure the process of sharing files between teachers and students; with features like Google Drive, teachers and students can share files with ease. Google Classroom was introduced as a feature of G-Suite for education, formerly Google Apps for education, on May 6, 2014, followed by its public release on August 12, 2014. In June 2015, Google announced a classroom Application Programming Interface (API) and a share button for websites, allowing school administrators and developers to further engage with Google Classroom. In March 2017, Google opened Google classroom to allow any personal Google users to join classes without the requirement of having a G-Suite (Google Suite) for Education account, and in April, it became possible for any personal Google user to create and teach a class. Google Classroom is one technology designed to enhance the teaching and learning experience of both the teachers and the students. Google Classroom is an education application suite offering productivity tools such

as email, documents and storage for students and teachers.

The tool offers opportunities for collaboration in real-time and the ability to work remotely, among many other features (Wikipedia, 2022). Students could become self-directed, and it produces a learning environment that improves students' knowledge and skills in the subject area (Hemrungle et al, 2017). Marwa, Mana & Sarah, (2019) identified three benefits of Google Classroom in the teaching and learning process, this includes; improving teachers' quality and providing the best experience for teachers while conducting the learning process. Students will finally be able to use the internet wisely and for education-based programmes. It saves time for both teachers and students as time will not be wasted on distributing physical materials. Tasks can be done quickly by adjusting schedules.

There was an estimated population of 1 0.2 million out of school children and in bringing a solution to this education emergency, the federal and state government and private sector implemented diverse useful and appropriate learning interventions with the use of technological platforms, internet based tools and traditional media to be an alternative avenue for teaching and learning against the closure of schools. Ofodu and Oluwadare (2021) posited that the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) paved way for online or virtual teaching and learning during the lockdown in Nigeria and even much after the lockdown, the impact of the covid-19 is much felt in the teaching and learning process.

One may not know what the future holds, e-learning appears to be the only learning system that can address this kind of issue. It appears the physical classroom method of teaching came to an absolute halt. E-Learning was introduced across board even though many schools have been practising digital pedagogy to complement instructional delivery. Some of the students seem to make use of computers, android, smartphones, radio, television and other electronic devices to aid home learning activities. E-learning could be a platform that makes the process of education more student-centred,

creative, flexible and easily accessible (Marwa, Mana & Sarah, 2020).

Moreover, the researcher observed that some students are familiar with the use of computers and e-learning platforms. It appears that some students are comfortable with computers, it seems some students can stay on the internet all day especially when they are chatting on social media platforms like Facebook, TikTok and WhatsApp. Youths widely use Instagram and TikTok and spend a substantial part of their time on different social network sites (Dada & Jimola, 2021). It appears that some teachers are not used to the operations of e-learning platforms, it seems that some of them do not have the technical know-how to operate a computer not to talk of applying them in a classroom setting. Some teachers are afraid to get involved in e-learning programmes because they think there would be many obstacles to overcome and that is why most teachers in secondary schools are not usually used to the operations of e-learning in their preparation for classroom teaching and learning experiences (Babalola & Onabanjo, 2013). This lack of expertise appears to have hindered the use of technologies in the classroom. Moreover, it appears that the content of the curriculum has not given enough support for the integration of computer technology into the teaching and learning process.

The researcher also observed that students' attitude and gender could have a major influence on their performance in Basic Science. Oniya (2018) affirmed that students' attitude is an integral part of learning and that it should, therefore, become an essential component of Basic Science learning. Attitude is the feeling either positive or negative, one has towards an idea, object or disposition which determines the performance of any learner towards learning. Some students seem to have the notion that spending many years in school is a huge waste of time, they seem to have the conviction that at the end of the day, a graduate might find himself in the labour market after investing so much in education. Festus and Ekpete (2012) also reported that students' positive attitudes to science correlate highly with their science achievement. It can then be adjudged that one's

attitude to something manifests in the way he/she would respond to issues that pertain to the thing. This is applicable to learning, which involves full concentration of the learners' attention. Thus, the attitude of students contributes immensely to their academic progress (Adedayo, 2015).

Gender could be seen as the distinction between male and female people based on their physical and behavioral traits. Studies on the relationship between gender and academic success have not yielded definitive results. According to certain findings (Akaayar, 2017; and Abuh, 2021), male and female students performed significantly differently, while in other studies the sex factor had no impact on the academic success of students Ode, et. al. (2019); Ibrahim et. al. (2021).

Statement of the Problem

Despite various efforts by stakeholders to improve teaching and learning of Basic Science at Junior Secondary School level because of its central role in the development of a nation economically and technologically, it is still characterized by low academic performance of students which is evident in both external and internal examinations and which might be as a result of Basic Science teachers that are still using conventional method to teach the subject.

The researcher observed through interview with some students in their various schools that attitude of students towards learning of science has been deteriorating due to complain that the subject is totally on abstract. Therefore, the study investigated the effects of Google classroom instruction on junior secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science in Osun state Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of Google classroom instruction on junior secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science in Osun state. Specifically, the study also determined;

a. the influence that attitude will have on students' academic performance in Basic Science;

b. examined the differences between the performance of male and female students in Basic Science

Research Question

One research question was raised to guide the study;

1. What is the influence of students, attitude towards Basic Science using Google Classroom?

Research Hypotheses

Three research hypotheses were postulated for the study;

1. There is no significant difference between students' academic performance in Google classroom and control group in Basic Science before treatment.

2. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group in Basic Science.

3. There is no significant difference between male and female students' academic performance in Google classroom and the control group.

Significance of the Study

Teachers, students, parents, curriculum designers, the government, other researchers, and society as large would all benefit from the study's conclusions.

The study to the teaching and learning process would give teachers of Basic Science and other teachers insight into importance and relevance of Google classroom and other online teaching platforms. The study would be of massive benefits to the students as it will expose the students to learning through Google classroom.

Curriculum planners, teacher's workshop and seminar organisers, and the government would find value in the study's findings as they would be provided with evidences that attitude, gender and the instructional strategy adopted by the Basic Science teacher could be factors affecting students' academic performance. If the findings of this study are put into practice, it would

inspire and prompt major stakeholders in education to revisit issues relating to teaching strategies, pedagogical expertise and students' characteristics in line with global educational requirements.

Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to effects of Google classroom instruction on junior secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science in Osun State. Only public JSS 2 pupils were used because they were readily available and they are not taking part in any external examination. Gender was only moderation variable.

Research Design

The study design adopted pre-test and post-test control group quasi-experimental research. It also employed descriptive survey design. The base line of the knowledge of the students that were used for the study was established by pre-test while the posttest was used after the treatment to measure academic performance.

The pattern of the design is shown below;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} O_1 & X_1 & O_2 \\ O_3 & X_c & O_4 \end{array}$$

Where:

O_1 and O_3 - Pre-test Observation

O_2 and O_4 - Post-test Observation

X_1 - Treatment via Google Classroom Instruction

X_c - Conventional Method of Instruction

Population

The population consisted of all 10,256 Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) two students in all the public secondary schools in Osun state as at the time of conducting this study.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample consisted of 120 junior secondary school two Basic Science students and they were chosen using a multi-stage sampling technique.

Stage one was the use of simple random sampling technique to select one senatorial district out of three senatorial districts in Osun state. Stage two involve the selection of two Local Government Area from the senatorial districts selected in Osun state through simple random sampling technique. Stage three involve the usage of Purposive sampling technique to select three secondary schools from each of the local government areas selected with the consideration of gender mixed-school that have access to internet devices such as smartphones and laptop computers. Stage four also involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select twenty students from each of the schools selected to make one hundred and twenty students used for the study

Research Instruments

Two instruments used for this study were Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) and Basic Science Students' Attitudinal Questionnaire (BSSAQ). BSPT consisted of two sections; section A and B. Section A was used to collect bio-data of the students while the section B contained twenty five multiple choice items drawn from the past questions of Junior Secondary School Certificate examination (JSSCE) which were related to the topics taught in the class during the treatment. The correct option picked by the students attract two marks while the wrong options attract zero.

BSSAQ consisted of two sections; section A and B. Section A was used to collect bio-data of the students while the section B contained twenty five items to elicit information on the attitude of students to the learning of Basic Science. The items in this section of the questionnaire was based on a 4-point Likert type scale with four options; Strongly Agree – 4 points, Agree – 3 points, Disagree - 2 points and Strongly Disagree – 1 point.

Validity of the Instruments

The face and content validities for BSPT and BSSAQ were ascertained with the help of two lecturers in Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State who were specialists in Science Education.

Reliability of the Instruments

The test-retest method was used to establish BSPT and BSSAQ by administering it to twenty JSS 2 Basic Science students from outside the sampled local government areas twice at the interval of two weeks in Osun state. Scores collected from the two tests were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the reliability coefficient of 0.89 and 0.78 were obtained which were used to adjudge the instruments to be reliable.

Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using inferential statistics. Specifically, the research question was answered by frequency count, mean and standard deviation, hypotheses one and two were analysed using t-test analysis and

hypothesis three was analysed using two-way ANOVA. The three hypotheses were tested at the significance level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question

What is the influence of students' attitude towards Basic Science using Google Classroom?

In order to answer the question, responses on items relating to student's attitude on their performance in Basic Science using Google Classroom were obtained and subjected to statistical analysis frequency count, mean and standard deviation. The result is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Influence of Students' Attitude on Their Performance in Basic Science using Google Classroom

S/N	Items on the influence of students' attitude in their performance using Google Classroom	Agree		Disagree		Mean	SD	Decision
		Freq.	Perc. %	Freq.	Perc. %			
1.	I feel comfortable interacting with my teacher in Google Classroom	116	96.7	4	3.3	1.97	0.18	Accept
2.	Learning through Google Classroom is fun and interesting	117	97.5	3	2.5	1.98	0.16	Accept
3.	Google Classroom has made me more productive	116	96.7	4	3.3	1.97	0.18	accept
4.	Learning with Google Classroom is too stressful	24	20	96	80	1.20	0.40	Reject
5.	I do not feel shy or afraid when I answer questions on Google Classroom	116	96.7	4	3.3	1.95	0.22	Accept
6.	I get distracted while learning with Google Classroom	31	25.8	89	74.2	1.26	0.44	Reject
7.	Our teacher makes use of online tools and apps to make the class very interesting	118	98.3	2	1.7	1.98	0.13	Accept
8.	I enjoy completing Google forms, quizzes and assignments on Google Classroom	118	98.3	2	1.7	1.98	0.13	Accept
9.	Google Classroom increases my thinking skills	118	98.3	2	1.7	1.98	0.13	Accept
10.	I feel motivated to learn while using Google Classroom	115	95.8	5	4.2	1.96	0.20	Accept

Table showed that using cutoff mean score of 1.5 for the rating scale, majority of the items had mean scores above the cutoff point while a few

had mean score below the cutoff point. This is an indication that students' attitude towards Basic Science using Google classroom in junior

secondary schools in Ekiti State is positive. With cutoff point of 1.5 and above, items relating to; I feel comfortable interacting with my teacher in Google Classroom (mean = 1.97), learning through Google Classroom is fun and interesting (mean = 1.98), Google Classroom has made me more productive (mean = 1.97), I do not feel shy or afraid when I answer questions on Google Classroom (mean = 1.95), Our teacher makes use of online tools and apps to make the class very interesting (mean = 1.98), I enjoy completing Google forms, quizzes and assignments on Google Classroom (mean = 1.98), Google Classroom increases my thinking skills (mean = 1.98), and I feel motivated to learn while using Google Classroom (mean = 1.96) had mean scores above cut off point and were accepted. However, the following items

fell below the cutoff point and were rejected; I get distracted while learning with Google Classroom (mean = 0.44), and earning with Google Classroom is too stressful (mean = 0.40).

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference between students' academic performance in Google classroom and control group before treatment.

In order to test the hypothesis, pre-test scores of students in both experimental and control group were subjected to statistical analysis using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. t-Test Analysis Showing Students' Scores in Google Classroom and Conventional Groups before Treatment

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p value
Google classroom	66	13.3788	2.50396	104	4.432	0.08
Conventional group	40	11.3250	1.95314			

Note: $P > 0.05$ (Not Significant)

The result in table 2 showed that the p value of 0.08 is higher than the significant value of 0.05. This implied that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between students' academic performance in Google classroom and control group before treatment in Basic Science was accepted. Therefore, there was no difference in the performance of students in the two groups. This means that both groups were homogeneous.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group.

In order to test the hypothesis, post-test scores of students in both experimental and control group were subjected to statistical analysis using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. t-Test Analysis Showing Post-Test Mean Score of Students in Google Classroom and Control Groups

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p value
Google classroom	66	17.1970	2.25470	104	11.245	0.000
Conventional group	40	12.6500	1.54505			

Note: $P > 0.05$ (Not Significant)

The table 3 showed that the p value of 0.000 was lesser than the significant value of 0.05. This

implied that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the post-test

mean score of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group was not accepted. Therefore, there was significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group. Looking at the mean values, the Google classroom students had higher mean value than the students in the control group which means that students exposed to Google classroom performed significantly than the student taught in the conventional group.

Hypotheses 3

There is no significant difference between male and female students' academic performance in Google classroom and the control group.

In order to test the hypothesis, post-test scores of male and female students in both experimental and control group were subjected to statistical analysis using two-way ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Two-Way ANOVA Analysis Showing Post-Test Scores of Male and Female Students in Both Experimental and Control Group

Source	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	519.08	3	173.03	42.083	0.000
Intercept	21917.95	1	21917.95	5330.767	0.000
Group*	500.90	1	500.90	121.827	0.000
Gender*	0.01	1	0.01	0.000	0.990
Group and Gender	3.91	1	3.91	0.951	0.332
Total	26343.00	106			

Note: P > 0.05 (Not Significant)

From the Test Between-Subjects Effects table above, the sig. value for group is 0.000 which is less than significant level of 0.005. It implies that there is significant difference between students' academic performance in Google classroom and control group. It means that there was difference in the performance. Also, the significant value for gender was 0.0990 which was greater than the significant of 0.05. It implies that there was no significant different in gender difference that is between male and female students' academic performance. It also means that male and female differ in their academic performance. The significant value for group and gender was 0.332 with F-value of 0.951 which was greater than significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there was no significant difference between male and female students' performance in Google classroom and control group.

Discussion

The finding showed that the influence of students' attitude on their performance in Basic

Science using Google classroom in secondary school in Ekiti State was very high. This implied that students have positive attitude to learning of Basic Science while using Google classroom. This oppose the observation by the researcher when he went round the schools to make enquire from the students before the treatment. Their show of interest could be as a result of introduction of Google classroom. The finding is in agreement with Olumorin et al (2022) that students have a positive attitude to the use of Google classroom.

The finding showed that there was no difference in the performance of students in the two groups. This means that both groups are homogeneous. This finding established the homogeneity of the two groups involved in the study prior to the treatment. In other words, it could be said that the knowledge base line for the two groups involved in the study were equal. Consequently, any significant different recorded in the academic performance of the students afterwards would not be ascribed to chance, but to the specific treatment applied. This could be as result that the students were taught by the

same topics and probably with the same instructional strategy before the treatment. This finding is supported by Oniya, (2018) that successful teaching and learning of subject matter depends partly on the adoption of relevant teaching method whose activities target mostly on learning senses.

The finding also showed that there was significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students exposed to Google classroom and the control group. And that the students taught through Google classroom performed better than the students taught with the conventional method in Basic Science. This means that teaching through Google classroom has very significant impact on the academic performance of students in Basic Science. This could be as a result that teachers and students find it easier to do some works such as distribution of assignments and discussion of subjects taught with the Google Classroom platform from the comfort of their homes while teaching and learning is ongoing. This is supported by Rakhmawati (2020) that there was significant effect after using Google classroom to teach. The findings is also in line with Oyarinde and Komolafe (2020) that Google classroom platform as an online learning delivery positively affected secondary school students' academic performance and their perception during COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

The findings of this study showed that there was no significant difference between male and female Basic Science students' performance in Google classroom and control group. The researcher opinioned that both male and female have same level of accessibility to the platform and that the platform is gender bias. The finding is in agreement with the Babalola and Oyinloye (2012) submission that male and female have equal chance of learning and acquiring tools during teaching and learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teaching Basic Science students with Google Classroom is more impactful than

the use of conventional physical classroom. It was also concluded that the use of Google classroom to teach Basic Science students was not gender bias.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Government should embark on more funds for the adequate training and retraining of Basic Science teachers on the use of Google Classroom.
2. Basic Science teachers should be encourage to integrate the use of Google Classroom while teaching in order to enhance students' attitude.
3. Basic Science teachers should be encouraged to explore and include the use of Google Classroom in their teaching and learning process.
4. Basic Science teachers should also sit up and embrace technologies and online facilities to boost their teaching activities.
5. Curriculum planners should make adequate and necessary upgrade to Basic Science curriculum in order to address students' individualism
6. School managements and government should fund and monitor the development of Google Classroom facilities in schools.

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